

Data management plan (DMP)

Investigating the Relationship Between IMDb Ratings and Worldwide Box Office Revenues (1980–2024)

IMDB-BOXOFFICE

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	30/11/2025	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project

TECHNISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
WIEN

Level of
distribution

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It is publicly available under DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17772206](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17772206).

FWF Data Management Plan (DMP)

I General Information																				
I.1 Administrative information	<p>PI: Máté Tóth, tothamate@gmail.com, ORCID iD: 0009-0005-2365-6971, TU Wien, ROR: ror.org/04d836q62, Principal Investigator</p> <p>FWF project number:</p> <p>Internal Project ID:</p> <p>DMP version: 1.0, 30.11.2025</p> <p>Contributors: Máté Tóth</p>																			
I.2 Data management responsibilities and resources	<p>Person responsible for data management and DMP: Máté Tóth, tothamate@gmail.com, ORCID: 0009-0005-2365-6971, TU Wien, ROR: ror.org/04d836q62</p> <p>Co-ordination of data management responsibilities across partners: Máté Tóth, tothamate@gmail.com, ORCID: 0009-0005-2365-6971, TU Wien, ROR: ror.org/04d836q62</p> <p>Resources costed in for RDM: There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.</p>																			
II Data Characteristics																				
II.1 Data description and collection or re-use of existing data	<p>Produced datasets:</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; text-align: center;"> <thead> <tr style="color: #4F81BD;"> <th style="padding: 5px;">dataset ID</th> <th style="padding: 5px;">title</th> <th style="padding: 5px;">type</th> <th style="padding: 5px;">format</th> <th style="padding: 5px;">estimated volume</th> <th style="padding: 5px;">contains sensitive data</th> <th style="padding: 5px;">description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px;">P1</td> <td style="padding: 5px;">Processed and derived movie dataset (1980–2024)</td> <td style="padding: 5px;">Standard office documents, Structured text, Images</td> <td style="padding: 5px;">CSV, PNG, IPYNB, MD, JSON</td> <td style="padding: 5px;">1 - 5 GB</td> <td style="padding: 5px;">no</td> <td style="padding: 5px;">This dataset contains all data produced during the project after cleaning, merging, and analysing the reused IMDb, Wikidata, and CPI datasets. It includes a processed CSV file with standardized variables (e.g., title,</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>						dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data	description	P1	Processed and derived movie dataset (1980–2024)	Standard office documents, Structured text, Images	CSV, PNG, IPYNB, MD, JSON	1 - 5 GB	no	This dataset contains all data produced during the project after cleaning, merging, and analysing the reused IMDb, Wikidata, and CPI datasets. It includes a processed CSV file with standardized variables (e.g., title,
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year, genres, IMDb rating, votes, raw and inflation-adjusted box office), as well as derived features such as genre dummy variables and log-transformed box office values. The dataset also contains model outputs, including linear regression and random forest predictions, residuals, and feature importance scores. In addition, figures (e.g., scatter plots, coefficient plots) and a Jupyter notebook documenting all processing steps are part of this dataset. All files follow FAIR principles and will be shared openly on GitHub and archived on Zenodo.

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data	description
R1	Dataset 1: Reused data	IMDb public datasets (https://datasets.imdbws.com/), Wikidata SPARQL endpoint (https://query.wikidata.org/), and U.S. CPI from the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics (https://download.bls.gov/pub/time.series/cu/).	IMDb: Non-commercial licence (IMDb non-commercial data licence) Wikidata: CC0 Public Domain BLS CPI: Public domain (US Government work)	no	This dataset consists of three publicly available sources: IMDb title.basics.tsv and title.ratings.tsv providing metadata, genres, ratings, and vote counts for films; Wikidata property P2142 providing worldwide box office values linked through IMDb IDs; and US CPI data used to adjust historical box office values for inflation. These datasets are reused without modification except for cleaning, filtering, and merging into the processed dataset.

	Methods and software used for data generation and reuse
III Documentation and Data Quality	
III.1 Metadata and documentation	<p>Data organisation, metadata, and documentation:</p> <p>I will follow a simple, reproducible folder structure that separates raw, processed, and derived data. Raw data (IMDb TSVs, Wikidata CSV, CPI data) will be stored in a read-only /data/raw/ folder to ensure it is not altered. All cleaning and transformation steps will produce files in /data/processed/, while model predictions, residuals, and figures will be stored in /data/derived/ and /results/. Versioning will be handled using Git and GitHub. I will create meaningful commit messages, tag the final release of the analysis, and archive the final version on Zenodo to mint a DOI. This ensures that all versions are recoverable, traceable, and permanently accessible.</p> <p>I will provide descriptive metadata for all datasets, including title, creator, date, licensing, and the original data sources used (IMDb, Wikidata, BLS CPI). Variable-level metadata will be included in a data dictionary that documents each column, its meaning, datatype, units, and any transformations applied. The processed dataset will also include provenance metadata such as the IMDb ID, Wikidata QID, and a field indicating the inflation index used. README files will describe file structure, dependencies, workflows, and the version of the code used to generate the dataset. Additional machine-actionable metadata (e.g., JSON or Markdown) will accompany the CSVs, enabling discovery and reuse. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.</p> <p>Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.</p> <p>As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.</p> <p>All steps of the workflow will be documented in a Jupyter notebook that shows exactly how the raw data was loaded, cleaned, merged, transformed, and analysed. This notebook will include explanations, code cells, and outputs so users can reproduce the results. A README file in the repository will describe the dataset structure, usage instructions, environment setup, and software versions. The repository will also contain a data dictionary with detailed descriptions of all variables.</p>
III.2 Data quality control	<p>Data quality control:</p> <p>The following data quality checks will be done: standardised data capture, data entry validation, representation with controlled vocabularies and Automated scripted quality checks (type enforcement, missing value detection, outlier handling, reproducible transformations in Jupyter notebook).</p>
IV Data Storage, Sharing, and Long-Term Preservation	
IV.1 Data storage and backup during the research process	<p>Storage and backup facilities:</p> <p>For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Máté Tóth (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator. The data will be stored on the servers of TU Wien.</p> <p>R1 (Dataset 1: Reused data) will be stored on TUfiles: TUfiles is a central and readily available network drive with daily backups and regular snapshots</p>

provided by Campus IT. It is suitable for storing data with moderate access requirements, but high availability demands that allows full control of allocating authorisations. Only authorized staff members will have access.

P1 (Processed and derived movie dataset (1980–2024)) will be stored on TUGitLab: TUGitLab is an application for managing repositories based on Git provided and managed by Campus IT. Our institute’s administrators will manage GitLab groups, assign project permissions, and appoint external project partners as additional GitLab users. This service is highly available and scalable on the Kubernetes platform.

Data security and protection of sensitive data:

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	no access
R1	writing	reading only	no access

IV.2 Data sharing and long-term preservation

Data publication and access conditions:

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	2026-01-01	Zenodo	DOI	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

ZENODO builds and operates a simple and innovative service that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to share and showcase multidisciplinary research results (data and publications) that are not part of the existing institutional or subject-based repositories of the research communities. ZENODO enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to: easily share the long tail of small research results in a wide variety of formats including text, spreadsheets, audio, video, and images across all fields of science. display their research results and get credited by making the research results citable and integrate them into existing reporting lines to funding agencies like the European Commission. easily access and reuse shared research results. <https://zenodo.org/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: The dataset will be shared as standard, non-proprietary CSV files, which can be opened with any spreadsheet software (e.g., LibreOffice, Excel) or read by common programming languages such as Python and R. The accompanying Jupyter notebook can be viewed directly on GitHub or executed in any environment that supports Python (e.g., Anaconda, Google Colab). No specialised or commercial software is required to access or reuse the dataset. All metadata will be provided in plain text or Markdown formats to ensure broad compatibility.

Long-term preservation and deletion of data:

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	Zenodo	10 years	Researchers, students, instructors, and anyone interested in film analytics, cultural data, or predictive modelling. It may also be used for teaching, exercises, or benchmarking machine learning models.

V Legal and Ethical Aspects

<p>V.1 Legal aspects</p>	<p>Personal data:</p> <p>At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.</p> <p>Intellectual property rights and rights of use:</p> <p>The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: Access to the datasets will be restricted to the project owner (myself) during the course of the project. I will have full control over reading and writing permissions for both the reused raw datasets and the processed dataset stored in TUfiles and TUGitLab. Since no personal or sensitive data is involved, no additional legal or ethical constraints apply. Redistribution of IMDb raw data is restricted by IMDb's licence, so only the processed and derived dataset will be shared publicly at the end of the project.</p>
<p>V.2 Ethical aspects</p>	<p>Ethical issues:</p> <p>No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.</p>